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Impact Of Monetary Policy On Economic Growth In Nigeria (2000-2019)

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ABSTRACT

This research work focused on money policy and economic growth: evidence from Nigeria (2000 – 2019). The research work made use of ex-post facto research design approach. The data used for this study were secondary comprising annual times series sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletins. The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) multiple regression technique was employed in data analysis. The study revealed that both monetary policy rate and cash reserve ratio had significant effects on economic growth in Nigeria while liquidity ratio had an insignificant effect on economic growth in Nigeria. Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended amongst others that in order to strengthen the economy of Nigeria, the Central Bank has to encourage the introduction of more financial instruments that are flexible enough to meet the liquidity requirements of investors. The government should also endeavour to make the financial sector less volatile and more viable as it is in developed countries as this will allow for smooth execution of the Central Bank monetary policies towards enhancing economic growth.

Keywords: money policy, economic growth, liquidity ratio

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Monetary policy as a technique of economic management to bring about sustainable economic growth and development has been the pursuit of nations while formal articulation of how it affects economic aggregates dates back to Adam Smith and later championed by the monetary economists. Monetary policy refers to a combination of measures designed to regulate the value, supply and cost of money in an economy in consonance with the expected level of economic activities (Onoh, 2013).

In Nigeria, monetary policy has been used since the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) was saddled with the responsibility of formulating and implementing monetary policies by Central Bank Act of 1958. This role has facilitated the emergence of active money market where Treasury Bills, a financial instrument used for open market operations and raising debt for government has grown in volume and value becoming a prominent earning asset for investors and source of balancing liquidity in the market. Another popular instrument of monetary policy (by the CBN) was the issuance of credit rationing guidelines, which primarily sets the rates of change for the components and aggregate commercial banks loans and advances to the private sector. On the other hand, the sectoral allocation of bank credit in CBN guidelines was to stimulate the productive sectors and thereby stem inflationary pressures while the fixing of interest rates at relatively low levels was done mainly to promote investment and growth. The objectives of monetary policy include price stability, maintenance of balance of payments equilibrium, promotion of employment and output growth and sustainable development. These objectives are necessary for the

attainment of internal and external balance and the promotion of long-run economic growth. The importance of price stability according to Akujobi (2012) derives from harmful effects of price volatility, which undermines the ability of policy makers to achieve other laudable macro-economic objectives. There is indeed a general consensus that domestic price fluctuation undermines the role of money as a store of value and frustrates investment and growth.

In Nigeria, nonetheless, there have been various regimes of monetary policy. Sometimes it could be tight and at other time it is loose mostly used to stabilize price. The economy has also witnessed times of expansion and contraction but evidently, the reported growth has not been a sustainable one as there are evidences of macro-economic instability. One can be tempted to ask if the period of economic growth could be attributed to period of appropriate monetary policy. Again could the periods of economic downfall be blamed on factors other than monetary policy effectiveness? What measures are to be considered if monetary policy would be effective in bringing about sustainable economic growth and development? These are questions this study would attempt to answer. Nigerian government has adopted various monetary policies through Central Bank of Nigeria over years to achieve economic growth. Despite the increasing emphasis on manipulation of monetary policies in Nigeria, the problem surrounding its economic growth still persists. Such problems include high unemployment rate, low investment and high rate of inflation, etc. These perceived problems are being claimed to have a fast decline in the economic growth of Nigeria. It, therefore, becomes necessary to highlight the monetary policy in Nigeria and examine the extent to which it has actually contributed to the growth in the economy.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Nigerian economy has adopted series of monetary policies to enhance economic growth through the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), but all these efforts have been faced with so many challenges as they seem not to have enhanced the level of welfare of citizens, hence, poor economic growth in real terms. Failure of the monetary policy in curbing price instability has caused growth instability as Nigeria's record of growth and development has been very poor. Despite the various monetary regimes that have been adopted by the Central Bank of Nigeria over the years, inflation still remains a major threat to Nigeria's economic growth. The dualistic nature of financial and product market in Nigeria constitutes of fundamental constraint militating against the formulation and implementation of efficient monetary policy.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

Generally, the objective of this study is to empirically evaluate the effect of monetary policy on economic growth in Nigeria. The specific objectives include to:

1. Examine the extent to which monetary policy rate affect economic growth in Nigeria.
2. Investigate the extent to which cash reserve ratio impact on economic growth in Nigeria.
3. Determine the extent to which liquidity ratio affect economic growth in Nigeria.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions will help immensely to achieve the objective of this study:

- (1) How does monetary policy rate affect economic growth in Nigeria?
- (2) To what extent does cash reserve ratio impact economic growth in Nigeria?
- (3) To what extent does liquidity ratio impact on economic growth in Nigeria?

1.5 Statement of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are raised in line with the objectives of the study

Ho₁: There is no significant impact of monetary policy rate on economic growth in Nigeria

Ho₂: Cash reserve ratio does not have a significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria

Ho₃: There is no significant effect of liquidity ratio on economic growth in Nigeria

1.6 Significance of the Study

The researcher believes that the study would be useful in the following parties:

- (1) **Students:** The research work will help expose students to the measures government takes to facilitate economic growth in Nigeria.

- (2) **Government:** It is the researcher's belief that the study will help government utilize its resources effectively and efficiently by strictly adhering to the recommendations raised in this study
- (3) **Researchers:** The study would help equip the researchers with materials on this topic as this study will contribute to literature on monetary policy and economic growth. It will also serve as a basis for further research in this and related areas.

1.7 Scope and Limitations of the Study

The economy is the largest component with lots of diverse and sometimes complex parts. This study will only focus on major growth components such as the real gross domestic product, but shall empirically investigate on the impact of the monetary policy on economic growth of Nigeria for the period 2000-2019.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Monetary Policy and Its Instruments

The term monetary policy has been defined by experts from many perspectives. According to Central Bank of Nigeria (2006), monetary policy concept was defined as "any policy measures designed by the federal government through the CBN to control cost availability and supply of credit". It is also referred to, as the regulation of money supply and interest rate by the CBN in order to control inflation and to stabilize the currency flow in an economy. Also CBN (1997), defined monetary policy as combination of measures designed to regulate the value, supply and cost of money on an economy in consonance with the expected levels of economic activities.

The Wikipedia encyclopedia (2015), defined monetary policy as the process by which the monetary authority of a country controls the supply of money, often targeting an inflation rate or interest to ensure price stability and general trust in the currency.

Instruments of monetary policy include:

- (a) **Liquidity Ratios:** These are classes of financial metrics used to determine a debtor's ability to pay off current debt obligations without raising external capital. Bankruptcy analysts and mortgage originators use liquidity ratios to evaluate going concern issues as liquidity measurements. Ratios indicate cash flow positioning.
- (b) **Moral Suasion:** This is an act of persuading a person or group to act in a certain way through rhetorical appeals, persuasion or implicit threats, as opposed to the use of outright coercion or force; it is commonly used in reference to central banks.
- (c) **Discount Rate:** This discount rate is the interest rate charged to commercial banks and other depository institutions for loans received from the Central Bank of Nigeria Central Bank of Nigeria's discount window. The discount rate also refers to the interest rate used in discounted cash flow analysis to determine the present value of future cash flows.
- (d) **Special Deposit:** This consists in the placing of specific kinds of money or property in the possession of the bank, with an obligation of the bank to return the identical thing deposited.
- (e) **Open Market:** The term open market is used generally to refer to an economic situation close to free trade. In a more specific technical sense the term refers to interbank trade in securities.
- (f) **Funding:** This is a method of converting short-term loans to medium and long-term loans. Treasury bills, which are short term loans, can be converted onto government to hold up funds of commercial banks for a long time these by making it difficult for them to lend.

2.1.2 Objectives of Monetary Policy

The monetary policy is aimed at achieving some objectives:

- (1) **Full Employment:** This is one of the foremost objectives of monetary policy. Full employment may be considered as a situation in which employment cannot be increased by increase in effective demand.
- (2) **Price Stability:** Price stability is very important in any given economy. The monetary control authorities should pursue policies that aim at stabilizing the price level, because fluctuations in

prices bring uncertainty and instability to the economy. Rising and falling processes are undesirable because they bring unnecessary loss to some and undue advantage to others. A policy of price stability keeps the value of money stable, eliminates cyclical fluctuations brings economic stability and also maintains a stable exchange rate.

- (3) **Balance of Payment Maintenance:** Monetary policy aimed at maintaining equilibrium in Balance of Payment. The achievement of this goal has been necessitated by the phenomenal growth in world trade. A deficit in the balance of payment will retard the attainment of other objectives because it leads to a sizable outflow of foreign reserves.
- (4) **Economic Growth and Development:** This refers to the process whereby the real per capita income of a country increases over a long period of time. Economic growth and development implies a sustained rise in goods and services and standard of living.

2.1.3 Concept of Economic Growth

Economic growth is an increase in the capacity of an economy to produce goods and services, compared from one period of time to another (Jhingan, 2000). It can be measured in nominal or real terms, the latter of which is adjusted for inflation. Traditionally, aggregate economic growth is measured in terms of Gross National Product (GNP) or Gross Domestic Product (GDP), although alternative metrics are sometimes used. It is also possible to achieve aggregate economic growth without an increase average marginal productivity through extra immigration or higher birth rates. A growing or more productive economy can make more goods and provide more services than before. However, some goods and services are considered more valuable than others. For instance, a smart phone is considered more valuable than a pair of socks. Growth has to be measured in the value of goods and services, not only the quantity. Higher economic growth is positively associated with an increased quality of life or standard of living.

Generating economic growth will involve the following:

- (i) The first way of generating economic growth is by discovering new or better economic resources.
- (ii) Another way of generating economic growth is to grow the labour force. All else equal, more workers generate more economic goods and services.
- (iii) Another good way of generating economic growth is to create superior technology or other capital goods whose rate of technical growth and capital growth is highly dependent on the rate of saving and investment, since savings and investment are necessary to engage in research and development.
- (iv) The fourth method of generating economic growth is by increasing specialization. This means labourers become more skilled at their crafts, raising their productivity through trial and error or simply more practice.

2.1.4 Concept of Productivity

Productivity is the key source of economic growth and competitiveness. A country's ability to improve its standard of living depends almost entirely on its ability to raise its output per worker, i.e. producing more goods and services for a given number of hours of works (Ngeyen, Huong and Lee, 2017). Economists use productivity growth to model the productive capacity of economies and determine their capacity utilization rates. This, in turn, is used to forecast business cycles and predict future levels of GDP growth. In addition, production capacity and utilization are used to assess demand and inflationary pressures.

2.1.5 Limitations of Monetary Policy in Nigeria

The expenditure of Nigeria reveals that monetary policy plays limited role in the country. The following arguments are given in support of this view:

- (1) The money and capital markets are underdeveloped. These markets lack bills, stocks, shares and other securities and as such, limit the successful implementation of the monetary policy.
- (2) There exist large informal financial sector, which hinders the success of monetary policy in Nigeria. Majority of the people live in rural areas where the use of formal financial institutions is limit.

- (3) A large number of non-bank financial institutions operate in the country, but they are not under the strict control of the Central Bank of Nigeria. Their operation tends to weaken the efficiency of the monetary policy.
- (4) Many banks in Nigeria possess high liquidity so that they are not influenced by the credit control of the Central Bank of Nigeria.
- (5) Foreign participation in the banking industry makes the monetary policy less effective. This is because the foreign participants in the industry can draw funds from their offices abroad when the Central Bank of Nigeria is following a contractionary monetary policy.
- (6) There are some affluent people in the economy who possess very low banking habit.

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 The Classical View of Monetary Policy

The classical economist's view of monetary policy is based on the quantity theory of money. The quantity theory of money is usually discussed in forms of fisherian equation of exchange which is given by the expression $MV = PV$.

In the expression, M denotes the supply of money over which the federal government has some control; V denotes the velocity of circulation which is the average number of times a currency is spent on final goods and services over the course of a year; P denotes the price level GDP. Hence PV represents current nominal GDP. The equation of exchange is an identity which states that the current market value of all final goods and services (nominal GDP) must equal the supply of money multiplied by the average number of times a currency is used in transaction in a given year. The classical economist believes that the economy is always at or near the natural level of real GDP. Thus, they assume that in the short run, the V in the equation of exchange is fixed. They further argue that the velocity of circulation of money tends to remain constant, so that V can also be regarded as fixed. Given that both Y and V are fixed, it follows that if the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) were to engage in expansionary (or contractionary) monetary policy, it will lead to an increase (or decrease) in money supply (M), the only effect would be to increase (or decrease) the price level (P), in direct proportion for the change in money supply (M). In other words, expansionary monetary policy can only lead to inflation and contractionary monetary policy can only lead to deflation of the price level.

2.2.2 The Monetarist View of Monetary Policy

Monetarist is a school of thought led by Milton Friedman. This school of thought is a modern variant of classical macro-economics. They developed a subtler and relevant version of the quantity theory of money. Like any school of thought, Friedman (1963), emphasize on the supply of money as the key factor affecting the well-being of the economy and as well, accepted the need for an effective monetary policy to stabilize an economy. He also has the notion that, in order to promote steady growth rate, money supply should grow at a fixed rate instead of being regulated and altered by the monetary authorities. Friedman equally argued that since money supply might be demanded for reasons other than anticipated transaction, it can be held in different forms such as money, bonds, equities physical goods and human capital. Each form of this wealth has unique characteristics of its own and a different yield. These effects will ultimately increase aggregate money demand and expand output. The monetarists acknowledged that the economy may not always be operating at the full employment level of real GDP. Thus, in the short-run, monetarists argue that expansionary monetary policies may increase the level of real GDP by increasing aggregate demand. However, in the long-run, when the economy is operating at the full employment level, they argue that the quantity theory remains a good approximation of the link between the supply of money, price level and the real GDP. Also, in the long-run expansionary monetary policy only leads to inflation and do not affect the level of real GDP.

2.3 Empirical Review

Over the years, there has been an unending debate on the effect of monetary policy on economic growth of some of the countries. Empirical works in this area are reviewed as below:

Onyeiwu (2012) examined the impact of monetary policy on the Nigerian economy using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method. The result showed that monetary policy represented by money supply exerts a positive impact on GDP growth and balance of payment but negative impact on rate of inflation and he concluded that CBN monetary policy is effective in regulating the liquidity of the economy which affects some macro-economic variables such as output, employment and prices.

Owalabi and Adegbite (2014), examined the impact of monetary policy on industrial growth of Nigerian economy using multiple regression analysis. They analyzed the relationship between manufacturing output, treasury bills deposit and lending rediscount rate and industrial growth, and found that the variables had significant effects on the industrial growth.

Chuku (2009) analyzed the effect of monetary policy innovations in Nigeria. The study used a Structural Vector Auto-Regression (SVAR) approach to trace the effects of monetary policy stock on output and prices in Nigeria. The study also analyzed the alternative policy instrument, that is, bond money (M2), minimum rediscount rate (MRR), and the real effective exchange rate (REER). The study found evidence that monetary policy innovations have both real and nominal effect on economic parameter depending on the policy variable selected.

Michael and Ebibai (2014), examined the impact of monetary policy on selected macro-economic variables such as gross domestic product, inflation and balance of payment in Nigeria using OLS regression analysis. The result shows that the provision of investment-friendly environment in Nigeria will increase the growth of GDP.

Akujobi (2012), investigated the impact of monetary policy instrument on economic development of Nigeria using multiple regression technique and found that treasury bill, minimum rediscount rate and liquidity rate have significant impact on economic development of Nigeria.

Okwo, Eze and Nwoha (2012) examined the effect of monetary policy outcomes on macro-economic stability in Nigeria. The study analyzed gross domestic product, credit to the private sector, net credit to the government and inflation using OLS technique. None of the variables were significant, which suggested that monetary policy as a policy option may have been inactive in influencing price stability.

Bernhard (2013), examined the channels of monetary transmission mechanism in Nigeria using Granger Causality test to estimate the relationship between the various channels and the selected macro-economic aggregates. The study showed that three channels of transmission were functional for inflation targeting. They include the interest rate, exchange rate and credit channels.

Omoke and Ugwuanyi (2010), investigated the relationship between inflation and output using co-integration and Granger Causality test analysis. They found that there was no existence of co-integrating vector in the series used. Thus, the result suggested that monetary stability can contribute towards price stability in Nigerian economy since the change in price level is mainly caused by money supply and thus concluded that inflation in Nigeria is to a large extent a monetary phenomenon.

Okoro (2013), examined the impact of monetary policy on Nigeria economic growth by testing the influence of interest rate, inflation, exchange rate, money supply and credit on GDP. Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test, Philips-perron Unit root test, co-integration test and Error Correction Model (ECM) techniques were employed. The results show the existence of long-run equilibrium relationship between monetary policy instrument and economic growth.

Umaru and Zubairu (2012), investigated the impact of inflation on economic growth and development in Nigeria between 1970 – 2010) through the application of Augmented Dickey-Fuller technique in testing the unit root property of the series and Granger Causality test of causation between GDP and inflation. The results of unit root suggest that all the variables in the model are stationary and the results of causality suggest that GDP causes inflation and not inflation causing GDP. The results also revealed that inflation possessed a positive impact on economic growth through encouraging productivity and output

level and on evolution of total factor productivity. A good performance of an economy in terms of per-capita growth may therefore be attributed to the rate of inflation in the country.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

Research design is a blueprint which guides the researcher in his scientific investigation and inquiry, Amaechi and Amara (2005). The *ex-post facto* research design will be adopted in obtaining, analyzing and interpretation of data relating to the objectives of the study. This also enables researchers to observe the research variables over a long period of time (Onwumere, 2009).

3.2 Nature and Source of Data

Secondary data will be used in this work. These will be obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin, journals as well as from other relevant documents.

3.3 Description of Research Variables

Dependent and independent variables will be made use of in this work.

3.3.1 Dependent Variable

The dependent variable in the study is the Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP). It shows the value of all output produce in a country valued at the cost of the factor services that went into production.

3.3.2 Independent Variables

The major explanatory variables in the study include: Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), Cash Reserve Ratios (CRR) and Liquidity Ratios (LQR).

3.4 Techniques of Analysis

The Ordinary Least Square (OLS) technique involving multiple regressions will be used in this study. The adoption of this technique is based on the premise that the OLS is assured to be the best linear unbiased estimator (Uremadu, 2007).

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \mu$$

Where:

Y	=	Dependent variable
β_0, β_1	=	Regression Coefficient
X_1	=	Independent Variable
μ	=	Error Term or Stochastic Variable

3.5 Model Specification

This model is adopted from the work of Okoro (2013).

$$RGDP = f(MPR, CRR)$$

However, it is modified to suit the objectives of the study as specified below:

$$RGDP = f(MPR, CRR, LQR)$$

Where:

RGDP	=	Real Gross Domestic Product
MPR	=	Monetary Policy Rate
CRR	=	Cash Reserve Ratios
LQR	=	Liquidity Ratios

Thus, the mathematical form of this model is:

$$RGDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \mu$$

The econometric form is:

$$RGDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MPR + \beta_2 CRR + \beta_3 LQR + \mu$$

4.0 PRESENTATION OF DATA, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Presentation of Data

The data used for the analysis comprises the dependent variable (Real gross domestic product) and the independent variables (monetary policy rate, liquidity ratio and cash reserve ratio). In what follows, the series of data are presented in Table 4.1 below:

Table 4.1: Presentation of Data

YEAR	Real gross domestic product (RGDP) N'billion	Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) %	Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR) %	Liquidity Ratio (LQR) %
2000	23,688.28	14.00	9.80	52.90
2001	25,267.54	20.50	10.80	52.45
2002	28,957.71	16.50	10.60	50.90
2003	31,709.45	15.00	10.00	50.48
2004	35,020.55	15.00	8.60	50.18
2005	37,474.95	13.00	9.70	55.70
2006	39,995.50	10.00	4.20	48.75
2007	42,922.41	9.50	2.80	44.25
2008	46,012.52	9.75	3.00	30.70
2009	49,856.10	6.00	1.25	30.43
2010	54,612.26	6.25	1.00	42.00
2011	57,511.04	12.00	8.00	49.72
2012	59,929.89	12.00	12.00	63.21
2013	63,218.72	12.00	12.00	38.32
2014	67,152.79	13.00	20.00	42.35
2015	69,023.93	11.00	20.00	46.00
2016	67,931.24	14.00	22.50	46.20
2017	68,490.98	14.00	22.50	54.80
2018	69,810.02	15.00	23.30	62.00
2019	71,387.83	15.60	24.00	69.30

Source: Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin (Various)

4.2 Data Analysis

The dataset presented in Table 4.1 were analysed using the descriptive statistics and regression analysis as shown below.

4.2.1 Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics captures the basic features (mean, maximum and minimum values, and standard deviation) of the dataset presented in Table 4.1 above

Table 4.2: Descriptive Statistics

	RGDP	MPR	CRR	LQR
Mean	48265.33	12.41667	10.48611	47.18556
Maximum	69023.93	20.50000	22.50000	63.21000
Minimum	23688.28	6.000000	1.000000	30.43000
Observations	18	18	18	18

Source: E-views 9.0 Output, 2022

From the results based on the descriptive statistics, the mean values indicates that average real gross domestic product (RGDP), monetary policy rate (MPR), liquidity ratio (LQR) and cash reserve ratio (CRR) are ₦48,265.33 billion, 12.41%, 47.18% and 10.48% respectively. With respect to the maximum and minimum values, it was found that the highest and lowest values for the series are RGDP (₦69,023.93 billion and ₦23,688.28 billion), MPR (20.50% and 6.00%), LQR (₦63.21% and 30.43%) and CRR (22.50% and 1.00%).

4.2.2 Regression Analysis

To find the effect of monetary policy variables on economic growth in Nigeria, the regression analysis was carried out. The results from the multiple regression are presented in Table 4.3 below:

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
MPR	-0.087620	0.017028	-5.145666	0.0001
CRR	0.044000	0.007548	5.829364	0.0000
LQR	-0.002684	0.006653	-0.403457	0.6927
C	11.48104	0.263120	43.63431	0.0000
R-Squared	0.774249			
Adjusted R-squared	0.725874			
F-statistics	16.00510			
Prob (F-statistics)	0.000084			

Source: E-views 9.0 Output 2023

The regression results reveal that the model has a good fit as shown by the adjusted R-squared of 0.725874. This implies that approximately 72% of the total variations in the dependent variable (RGDP) was jointly explained by the explanatory variables (CRR, LQR and MPR), while the remaining 28% was due to the error term. The probability value (0.000084) of the F-statistics shows that the overall regression model is stable such that the explanatory variables jointly and significantly predicted the total changes in the dependent variable (RGDP).

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: Monetary policy rate does not have a significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

The results show that monetary policy rate (MPR) has a negative relationship with economic growth (proxied by RGDP). Following the estimated coefficient of monetary policy rate (MPR), it was found that an increase in monetary policy caused 0.087620 decrease in RGDP. This implies that over the period of study, monetary policy rate (MPR) which is a core determinant of other interest rates has not contributed positively to economic growth of Nigeria. This could be due to the fact that MPR in Nigeria is high, hence economic participants find it difficult to access funds due to high interest rates which results to low productivity and economic growth. This finding is in line with those of Nasko (2016); Ngeyen, Houg and Le (2017) that increased monetary policy rate discourages borrowings which results to low economic growth. Furthermore, the p-value ($0.001 < 0.05$) reveals that monetary policy rate has a significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria. Based on this finding, the null hypothesis (H₀₁) was rejected.

H₀₂: Cash reserve ratio does not have a significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria.

Based on the estimated coefficient of cash reserve ratio (CRR), it was found that cash reserve ratio has a positive and significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria. The coefficient of CRR suggests that an increase in CRR caused about 0.044000 increase in RGDP. This implies that the prescribed cash reserve ratio caused a positive effect on economic growth over the period of study. A plausible reason for this could be that the more reserve banks accumulate boosts the confidence of the public to commit their funds to the banks in form of deposits. According to Okafor and Uchendu (2014), banks usually fall back to their reserves to meet customers' loan demands for productivity activities. The p-value ($0.0000 < 0.05$) reveals that the cash reserve ratio has a significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected (H₀₂) and the alternative hypothesis accepted that cash reserve ratio economic growth in Nigeria. Hence, the null hypothesis accepted that cash reserve ratio (CRR) has a significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

H₀₃: Liquidity ratio does not have a significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

The estimated coefficient of liquidity ratio (LQR) indicates that an increase in liquidity ratio caused about 0.002684 decrease in economic growth (proxied by RGDP). This could be due to lack of funds available to the banks to meet their loan obligations. This is in line with Enyioko (2012) that banks' inability to meet customers loan demand due to lack of liquidity results to decrease in economic growth. However,

the p-value ($0.6927 > 0.05$) indicates that liquidity ratio as a monetary policy variable does not have a significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

4.4 discussion of findings

The study analyzed the effect of monetary policy on economic growth in Nigeria using time series data from 2000 to 2019. Based on the regression analysis, the following findings were made:

1. Monetary policy rate has a negative and significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.
2. Cash reserve ratio has a positive and significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.
3. Liquidity ratio has a negative and insignificant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

5.0 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

Based on the analysis of the data presented in the study, the following findings were made:

- (1) Monetary policy rate has a negative and significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.
- (2) Cash reserve ratio has a positive and significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.
- (3) Liquidity ratio has a negative and insignificant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

5.2 Conclusion

Generally, this research work has demonstrated monetary policy variables as potent instruments to effect economic growth subject to policy variable adopted by the monetary authorities. The study affirms that implementing monetary policy in Nigeria could attract increased economic growth if well implemented. Based on the analysis, it was found that the most potent monetary policy are monetary policy rate and reserve ratio following their respective significant p-values. It was therefore conclude that most times, the incapability of the monetary policies to efficiently and effectively exploit its policy objective could be a function of pitfall of policy instruments adopted which restricts its contributions to economic progress in Nigeria.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. In order to strengthen the economy of Nigeria, the Central Bank has to encourage the introduction of more financial instruments that are flexible enough to meet the liquidity requirements of investors.
2. The government should also endeavour to make the financial sector less volatile and more viable as it is in developed countries as this will allow for smooth execution of the Central Bank monetary policies towards enhancing economic growth.
3. The Nigerian government should as well strive to limit the volatility of the financial system and make it more viable, efficient and effective as we have in developed economies. This will automatically allow for smooth monetary policy execution by the CBN.

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**APPENDIX
Data on RGDP, MPR, CRR and LQR**

YEAR	Real gross domestic product (RGDP) N'billion	Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) %	Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR) %	Liquidity Ratio (LQR) %
2000	23,688.28	14.00	9.80	52.90
2001	25,267.54	20.50	10.80	52.45
2002	28,957.71	16.50	10.60	50.90
2003	31,709.45	15.00	10.00	50.48
2004	35,020.55	15.00	8.60	50.18
2005	37,474.95	13.00	9.70	55.70
2006	39,995.50	10.00	4.20	48.75
2007	42,922.41	9.50	2.80	44.25
2008	46,012.52	9.75	3.00	30.70
2009	49,856.10	6.00	1.25	30.43
2010	54,612.26	6.25	1.00	42.00
2011	57,511.04	12.00	8.00	49.72
2012	59,929.89	12.00	12.00	63.21
2013	63,218.72	12.00	12.00	38.32
2014	67,152.79	13.00	20.00	42.35
2015	69,023.93	11.00	20.00	46.00
2016	67,931.24	14.00	22.50	46.20
2017	68,490.98	14.00	22.50	54.80
2018	69,810.02	15.00	23.30	62.00
2019	71,387.83	15.60	24.00	69.30

Source: Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin (Various)